

Synthesis and evaluation of neurotoxicity and neuroprotection at the subcellular level of prospective pyrrole-based azomethines

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Abstract

The synthesis of four new *N*-pyrrolyl azomethines is presented. A classical Paal-Knorr cyclization was used for the synthesis of the initial *N*-pyrrolyl hydrazide, whereas the final hydrazones were obtained on a micro-synthesis scale, assuring reduced harmful emissions, reagent economy, and yields of approximately 51–69%. The compound structures were elucidated by infrared (IR), ¹H, and ¹³C nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectral analyses, and the obtained results were consistent with the assigned structures. The purity of the substances was confirmed by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) characteristics and corresponding melting points. In addition, the neurotoxicity and neuroprotection properties of the studied molecules were assessed at three subcellular levels. The results on synaptosomal, mitochondrial, and microsomal fractions isolated from rat brains indicated that all evaluated compounds have low neurotoxicity. The experiments on the neuroprotective effects, based on three oxidative models, including the 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA) model; the *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (*t*-BuOOH)-induced oxidative stress model; and the classical non-enzymatic lipid peroxidation model based on iron/ascorbate-induced peroxidation, indicated the compounds as potential neuroprotective and antioxidant agents.

Keywords

Antioxidant activity, neuroprotection, neurotoxicity, oxidative stress, pyrrole-based azomethines, spectral analysis, subcellular models, synthesis

Introduction

Traditionally, mitochondria were viewed mainly as double-membrane organelles responsible for producing ATP through cellular respiration. Today, they are recognized as central regulators of cellular function, maintaining homeostasis and controlling processes such as apoptosis, calcium signaling, and oxidative stress (Ricci et al. 2004; Kim et al. 2008; Diano and Horvath 2012).

Mitochondria are double-membrane organelles with distinct outer and inner membranes that define the inter-membrane space and matrix (Frey and Mannella 2000). The inner membrane contains the respiratory chain and oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS) complexes essential for ATP production and cellular survival (Frey and Mannella 2000). Mitochondrial morphology and distribution vary according to cellular function and stress conditions (Picard et al. 2011). In neurons, mitochondria

additionally regulate calcium homeostasis, membrane excitability, neurotransmission, and synaptic plasticity and retain autonomous gene expression machinery encoded by mitochondrial DNA (mt DNA) (Frey and Mannella 2000; Rose et al. 2017).

Given the complexity of mitochondrial biogenesis and dynamics, mitochondria are particularly susceptible to structural and functional damage. Mitochondrial dysfunction impairs ATP synthesis, increases reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, and disrupts calcium homeostasis. While physiological levels of ROS regulate signaling pathways, including those involved in axonal development (Nunnari and Suomalainen 2012), excessive ROS promotes oxidative damage and apoptosis (Fleury et al. 2002; Beckhauser et al. 2016). These mechanisms contribute to the progressive neuronal loss observed in neurodegenerative disorders such as Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, Huntington's disease, epilepsy, and schizophrenia (Bezprozvanny 2009; Liochev 2013; Puttachary et al. 2015).

Neuronal polarity and compartmentalization require precise mitochondrial trafficking and distribution (Horton and Ehlers 2003; Barnes and Polleux 2009; Lewis et al. 2013; Gumy and Hoogenraad 2018). In cortical neurons, mitochondria display compartment-specific morphology, appearing elongated and abundant in dendrites but more discrete and sparsely distributed in axons (Popov et al. 2005; Chang and Reynolds 2006; Lee et al. 2018). Mitochondrial morphology is regulated by biogenesis, trafficking, fission, fusion, and mitophagy, with dynamics playing a central role (Chen and Chan 2009; Kraus et al. 2021).

Mitochondrial dysfunction can be assessed by measuring mitochondrial membrane potential ($\Delta\psi_m$) as an indicator of proton motive force (Nicholls and Budd 2000; Nicholls 2006; Ward et al. 2007; Nicholls and Ferguson 2013), oxygen consumption rate (OCR) as a measure of respiratory activity (Brand and Nicholls 2011; Dranka et al. 2011), and circulating cell-free mitochondrial DNA (cf-mtDNA), a sensitive biomarker of cellular injury and disease severity (de Miranda et al. 2021; McClintock et al. 2022; de Miranda et al. 2024). Additional markers of mitochondrial oxidative stress, including SOD1, malondialdehyde (MDA), F2-isoprostanes, glutathione, and coenzyme Q, are associated with aging and diverse pathological conditions (Ito et al. 2019).

This study employs primary rodent neuronal cultures, a well-established and highly specialized experimental platform for investigating the molecular mechanisms underlying neurodegenerative processes and assessing the neurotoxicity and neuroprotection of possible biologically active azomethines.

Over the past few decades, increasing scientific interest has been directed toward pyrrole and pyrrolopyrimidine derivatives due to their significant biological relevance, including antitumor, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, antihistaminic, antimalarial, antiparkinsonian, antioxidant, and antiviral activities (Kondeva-Burdina et al. 2022).

Hydrazone derivatives containing an azomethine functional group represent an important class of chemical com-

pounds with broad relevance to the development of novel pharmaceutical agents. It has been demonstrated that the hydrazone moiety plays a significant role in the anti-infective activity of these compounds (Mahajan et al. 2011).

Thus, the current manuscript is focused on combining the active principles of pyrroles and azomethines and evaluating their possible neurotoxicity and neuroprotection at cellular and subcellular levels.

Materials and methods

Chemistry

All chemicals and reagents for synthesis were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). The commercially unavailable initial hydrazide was synthesized in the laboratory according to the procedure described previously (Tzankova et al. 2017).

General procedure for synthesis of the final azomethine representatives

The initial carbohydrazide ethyl 5-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-(1-hydrazinyl-1-oxo-3-phenylpropan-2-yl)-2-methyl-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate (III) (1.5 mmol) and any of the carbonyl partners 1, 2, 4, or 6 (1.5 mmol) were dissolved in 4.5 mL glacial acetic acid in a 5 mL reaction vial. The mixture was stirred at 100 °C for 7 h to complete the reaction under TLC control. The synthesis progress was controlled by TLC on aluminum sheets Silicagel 60 F254 (Merck, Germany), using CHCl₃/ethanol (10:1) as a mobile phase. The obtained products were isolated by cooling the reaction mixture, followed by the addition of cold water until complete precipitation occurred. The precipitate was collected by vacuum filtration and washed thoroughly to ensure complete removal of residual acetic acid. If necessary, the final products were further purified by recrystallization from an appropriate solvent.

The melting points of the synthesized azomethine-containing compounds were determined using the capillary method on a digital melting point apparatus IA 9200 (Electrothermal, UK) and were not corrected. Prior to analysis, all samples were recrystallized and dried to constant weight to remove residual solvents. Approximately 1–2 mg of each compound was finely powdered and packed into a sealed glass capillary, forming a sample column of 2–3 mm in height. The capillaries were placed in the heating block of the apparatus, and the samples were heated at a controlled rate of 1–2 °C min⁻¹ in the temperature range close to the expected melting point. The temperatures corresponding to the onset of melting and complete liquefaction were recorded. The melting point was reported as the temperature interval between these two values. Each measurement was performed in duplicate, and the results showed good reproducibility ($\Delta T \leq 1$ °C). No decomposition was observed below 150 °C.

The newly obtained molecules were elucidated through an appropriate spectral methodology, and their purity was

confirmed by melting point determination, TLC characteristics, and elemental analysis. The corresponding values are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. IDs, melting points, TLC characteristics, and yields of the new hydrazones.

IDs	Melting points (°C)	TLC (Rf)	Yield (%)
Y1	92.6	0.67	51
Y2	100.1	0.17	64.2
Y4	129.0	0.31	50.1
Y6	128.9	0.69	69

The structures of the new compounds were proven by IR spectra within the 400–4000 cm^{-1} range recorded on a Nicolet iS10 FT-IR spectrometer using the attenuated total reflectance (ATR) technique with a Smart iTR adapter (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The corresponding ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were registered on a Bruker Spectrospin WM600 spectrometer (Bruker, Switzerland) at 600 MHz as δ (ppm) relative to TMS as the internal standard. All NH protons were D_2O exchangeable.

The IUPAC names of the newly synthesized hydrazones, together with the interpretation of their IR and ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra, are presented below:

(E)-5-(4-bromophenyl)-1-(1-(2-(2-fluorobenzylidene)hydrazinyl)-1-oxo-3-phenylpropan-2-yl)-2-methyl-1H-pyrrol-3-yl propionate (Y1): IR (ATR): 3150 (NH), 2000–2820 (CH_3 and CH_2), 1680 (COOC_2H_5), 1640 (Amide I), 1520 (Amide II), 1240 (C-O), 830 (p-disubstituted C_6H_4), 680, 750 (monosubstituted C_6H_5); ^1H NMR (at 600 MHz, in DMSO-d_6): 1.09 (t, 3H), 2.27 (s, 3H), 3.40 (m, 1H), 3.75 (m, 1H), 5.02 (q, 2H, $J = 7.04$ Hz), 5.02 (q, 1H), 6.05 (s, 1H), 6.05 (s, 2H), 6.68 (d, 2H), 7.27 (t, 1H), 7.27 (d, 1H), 7.27 (t, 2H), 7.27 (m, 1H), 7.36 (m, 2H), 7.36 (m, 1H), 7.27 (s, 1H), 8.54 (s, 1H), 8.54 (s, 1H), 8.54 (m, 1H). ^{13}C NMR (at 600 MHz, in DMSO-d_6): 160.8, 160.8, 156.8, 156.8, 136.7, 136.7, 132.6, 132.1, 132.1, 132.1, 132.1, 132.1, 128.6, 128.6, 127.7, 123.7, 121.7, 121.7, 115.6, 115.6, 109.6, 59.9, 59.9, 27.2, 9.4, 9.4

(E)-1-(4-((4-acetamidobenzylidene)amino)-3-oxo-1-phenylbutan-2-yl)-5-(4-bromophenyl)-2-methyl-1H-pyrrol-3-yl propionate (Y2): IR (ATR): 3290 (NH), 1709 (COOC_2H_5), 1674 (Amide I), 1569 (Amide II), 1250 (C-O), 815 (p-disubstituted C_6H_4), 698 (monosubstituted C_6H_5); ^1H NMR (at 600 MHz, in DMSO-d_6): 1.09 (t, 3H), 2.04 (s, 6H), 2.71 (s, 3H), 2.71 (t, 1H), 4.71 (d, 1H), 4.71 (m, 2H), 4.94 (q, 1H), 6.05 (s, 1H), 6.05 (s, 2H), 6.05 (d, 2H), 7.27 (m, 2H), 7.27 (m, 1H), 7.27 (s, 1H), 7.29 (d, 2H), 7.78 (m, 1H), 7.78 (m, 2H), 7.78–8.65 (m, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (at 600 MHz, in DMSO-d_6): 168.9, 168.9, 168.9, 136.7, 136.7, 134.2, 132.1, 132.1, 130.6, 128.6, 128.6, 128.6, 128.6, 127.7, 123.7, 123.7, 115.6, 109.6, 77.1, 59.9, 59.9, 27.2, 24.0, 9.4, 9.4

(E)-5-(4-bromophenyl)-1-(4-((2-fluoro-5-nitrobenzylidene)amino)-3-oxo-1-phenylbutan-2-yl)-2-methyl-1H-pyrrol-3-yl propionate (Y4): IR (ATR): 3523 (NH), 3192 (CH_3 and

CH_2), 1694 (COOC_2H_5), 1660 (Amide I), 1568 (Amide II), 1241 (C-O), 812 (p-disubstituted C_6H_4), 697 (monosubstituted C_6H_5); ^1H NMR (at 600 MHz, in DMSO-d_6): 1.09–1.09 (m, 3H), 2.71 (s, 3H), 2.71 (s, 1H), 2.71–2.71 (m, 1H), 4.71–4.71 (q, 1H), 4.71 (s, 3H), 4.71–4.71 (m, 2H), 4.94–4.94 (q, 1H), 6.05 (s, 1H), 6.05 (s, 2H), 6.05–6.05 (q, 2H), 7.27–7.27 (m, 2H), 7.27 (m, 1H), 7.27 (m, 1H), 7.27–7.29 (d, 2H), 7.29, 7.29 (d, 2H), 7.40 (s, 1H), 8.50 (m, 1H); ^{13}C NMR (at 600 MHz, in DMSO-d_6): 165.7, 165.7, 165.7, 143.6, 136.7, 136.7, 132.1, 132.1, 132.1, 132.1, 128.9, 128.9, 128.6, 128.6, 127.7, 122.5, 121.7, 118.5, 109.6, 109.6, 59.9, 59.9, 27.2, 9.4, 9.4, 9.4

(E)-5-(4-bromophenyl)-1-(4-((4-chlorobenzylidene)amino)-3-oxo-1-phenylbutan-2-yl)-2-methyl-1H-pyrrol-3-yl propionate (Y6): IR (ATR): 3280 (NH), 1717 (COOC_2H_5), 1668 (Amide I), 1570 (Amide II), 1250 (C-O), 812 (p-disubstituted C_6H_4), 700 (monosubstituted C_6H_5); ^1H NMR (at 600 MHz, in DMSO-d_6): 1.09 (t, 3H), 2.14 (s, 3H), 2.71 (s, 3H), 2.71 (t, 1H), 4.71–4.71 (q, 1H), 4.71–4.71 (q, 2H), 4.94–4.94 (q, 1H), 6.05 (s, 1H), 6.05 (s, 2H), 6.05, 6.05 (d, 2H), 6.05–6.05 (d, 1H), 7.27–7.27 (m, 2H), 7.27–7.27 (m, 1H), 7.27 (s, 1H), 7.29–7.29 (d, 2H), 7.78–7.78 (m, 2H), 8.17–8.17 (d, 2H); ^{13}C NMR (at 600 MHz, in DMSO-d_6): 160.8, 160.8, 160.8, 136.6, 136.6, 134.5, 132.1, 130.6, 130.6, 128.9, 128.9, 128.6, 128.6, 128.6, 127.7, 123.7, 109.6, 109.6, 107.2, 59.9, 59.9, 59.9, 27.2, 9.4, 9.4

Pharmacology evaluations

Animals

Nine male Wistar rats with body weights of 200–250 g were used. They were housed in plexiglass cages (three per cage) in a 12/12 light/dark cycle under standard laboratory conditions (ambient temperature $20^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and humidity $72\% \pm 4\%$), with free access to water and standard pelleted rat food 53-3, produced according to ISO 9001:2008. The animals were purchased from the National Breeding Centre, Sofia, Bulgaria. Seven days of acclimatization were allowed before the commencement of the study, and a veterinary physician monitored the health of the animals regularly. The vivarium (certificate of registration of farm № 0072/01.08.2007) was inspected by the Bulgarian Drug Agency to check the husbandry conditions (№ A-11-1081/03.11.2011).

All performed procedures were approved by the Institutional Animal Care Committee of the Medical University of Sofia (Bulgarian Agency for Food Safety with Permission No. 190, approved on 6 February 2020, and valid until 2026). The principles stated in the European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals used for Experimental and Other Scientific Purposes (ETS 123) were strictly followed throughout the experiment. Brains were taken from rats immediately after decapitation and stored on ice until needed.

Subcellular in vitro studies

Two types of buffers were used for the isolation of rat brain synaptosomes and mitochondria. Buffer A was 5 mM HEPES and 0.32 M sucrose; Buffer B was 290 mM NaCl, 0.95 mM $\text{MgCl}_2 \times 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 10 mM KCl,

2.4 mM $\text{CaCl}_2 \times 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2.1 mM NaH_2PO_4 , 44 mM HEPES, and 13 mM D-glucose. For gradient centrifugation, Percoll reagent was used. A stock solution of 90% Percoll was used to prepare 16%, 10%, and 7.5% solutions. All solutions were used as described below.

Immediately after harvesting, synaptosomes, microsomes, and mitochondria were incubated with compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6 for 1 h.

For assessing the possible neurotoxicity of compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6, the subcellular fractions were incubated with 100 μM of them for 1 h, and for evaluating their possible neuroprotective and antioxidant activities in different models of neurotoxicity, the subcellular fractions were pre-incubated with 50 μM of them for 30 min and then together for 1 h with the neurotoxic agents.

The protein measurement of all subcellular fractions was performed by the method of Lowry et al. (1951).

Rat brain synaptosomes— isolation and incubation

The synaptosomes were prepared from rat brains by multiple subcellular fractionations using a Percoll gradient (Taupin et al. 1994).

Synaptosomal viability

After incubation, the synaptosomes were centrifuged three times at $15,000 \times g$ for 1 min. The MTT test was performed to determine synaptosomal vitality by the method described by Mungarro-Menchaca et al. (2002).

Determination of reduced glutathione (GSH)

The level of reduced glutathione (GSH) was determined by measuring the non-protein SH groups after precipitation of the proteins with trichloroacetic acid (TCA). The presence of thiols in the supernatant was determined using Ellman reagent. The resulting yellow color was measured spectrophotometrically ($\lambda = 412 \text{ nm}$) (Robyt et al. 1971).

Rat brain microsomes—preparation

The brain was homogenized in nine volumes of 0.1 M Tris buffer containing 0.1 mM dithiothreitol, 0.1 mM phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride, 0.2 mM EDTA, 1.15% KCl, and 20% (*v/v*) glycerol at pH 7.4. The homogenate was centrifuged twice at $17,000 \times g$ for 30 min. The supernatants from both centrifugations were combined and centrifuged twice at $100,000 \times g$ for 1 h. The resulting pellet was frozen in Tris until needed (Ravindranath and Anandatheerthavarada 1990).

Scheme 1. General synthesis of the target azomethines Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6.

FeSO₄/ascorbic acid-induced lipid peroxidation (LPO)

The lipid peroxidation (LPO) was started with a solution of 20 μM iron sulfate (FeSO_4) and 0.5 mM ascorbic acid (Mansuy et al. 1986).

Malondialdehyde (MDA) assay

The quantity of the lipid peroxidation product malondialdehyde (MDA) was assessed using the method described by Deby and Goutier (1990).

Rat brain mitochondria— isolation

The mitochondria were prepared by multiple differential fractionation using a Percoll gradient (Sims and Anderson 2008).

Tert-butyl hydroperoxide (t-BuOOH)-induced oxidative stress

The mitochondria were incubated with 75 μM *t*-BuOOH (Karlsson et al. 2001).

Lipid peroxidation assay

After incubation of the mitochondria, 0.3 mL of 0.2% TBA and 0.25 mL of sulfuric acid (0.05 M) were added to stop the reaction. The tubes were maintained at 100 °C for 30 min. In the next stage, centrifugation of the tubes was carried out at $3500 \times g$ for 10 min. Assessment of the total quantity of MDA formed in each sample was measured in the supernatant at 532 nm (Shirani et al. 2019).

Measurement of GSH content

After incubation of mitochondria, 0.04% DTNB was mixed with the mitochondrial suspensions in 0.1 M phosphate buffers (pH 7.4). The absorbance of the yellow product was measured at 412 nm (Shirani et al. 2019).

Results and discussion

The investigated azomethine compounds were synthesized via a classical condensation reaction between the target hydrazide and the corresponding aldehydes. The required amount of aldehyde was calculated stoichiometrically based on the amount of hydrazide used. Immediately after mixing the reactants, glacial acetic acid was added to the reaction mixture as a catalyst (Scheme 1).

The structures of the carbonyl partners 1, 2, 4, and 6 are presented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Structures of the used carbonyl partners 1, 2, 4, and 6.

The reaction mechanism proceeds through several consecutive steps. First, in the presence of glacial acetic acid, the carbonyl oxygen of the aldehyde becomes partially protonated, which increases the electrophilicity of the carbonyl carbon and facilitates nucleophilic attack. The terminal amino group of the hydrazide ($-\text{NH}_2$ in $-\text{CONHNH}_2$) then attacks the activated carbonyl carbon. In the acidic medium, rapid proton transfer steps follow, during which the hydroxyl group is protonated and converted into a better leaving group, while the nitrogen atom becomes properly oriented for the formation of an azomethine ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) bond. Subsequent dehydration, involving the elimination of a water molecule, constitutes a key step and leads to the formation of the azomethine system. Finally, deprotonation yields the stable end product, namely the corresponding acylhydrazone.

After completion of the synthesis, the obtained compounds were subjected to a comprehensive physicochemical characterization to establish their structure, purity, and individuality. Within this characterization, melting point determination was employed as a primary and mandatory analytical parameter, as it provides essential information regarding the purity of the synthesized organic compounds and allows comparison with literature data for structurally related compounds.

The synthesized azomethine compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6 were obtained as solid substances and characterized by determination of their melting points. The experimentally determined melting points ranged from 92.6 to 129.0 °C (Table 1), which is typical for azomethine derivatives and indicates good purity of the products after purification. Compound Y1 exhibited the lowest melting point (92.6 °C), while Y2 showed a moderate increase (100.1 °C), suggesting differences in intermolecular interactions and crystal packing. In contrast, compounds Y4 and Y6 displayed significantly higher and closely related melting points (129.0 and 128.9 °C, respectively), indicative of similar structural features and a more stable crystal lattice, likely resulting from enhanced π - π interactions and increased molecular polarity. No thermal decomposition was observed below 150 °C.

The relatively narrow melting point values and the absence of observable decomposition within the investigated temperature range indicate good purity of the synthesized compounds after purification.

The neurotoxicity of the target hydrazones was evaluated on three subcellular fractions: isolated rat-brain synaptosomes, isolated rat-brain mitochondria, and isolated rat-brain microsomes.

Synaptosomes, mitochondria, and microsomes are well-established subcellular models widely used for the mechanistic assessment of neurotoxicity and neuroprotection. Synaptosomes are resealed presynaptic nerve terminals that retain functional neurotransmitter uptake, storage, and calcium-dependent release, enabling sensitive evaluation of synaptic dysfunction, excitotoxicity, and oxidative stress—early events in neurodegeneration (Whittaker 1959; Nicholls and Sihra 1986). Isolated brain mitochondria allow direct measurement of oxidative phosphorylation, respiratory chain complex activity, membrane potential, and reactive oxygen species generation, providing precise insight into toxin-induced bioenergetic failure and the efficacy of mitochondria-targeted protective strategies (Chance and Williams 1955; Nicholls and Budd 2000). Microsomes, derived primarily from the endoplasmic reticulum, contain cytochrome P450 monooxygenase systems and are therefore essential for studying xenobiotic metabolism, metabolic activation of neurotoxicants, and lipid peroxidation processes (Halliwell and Gutteridge 1990; Guengerich 2008). Together, these complementary subcellular systems permit controlled, reproducible investigation of molecular mechanisms underlying neuronal injury and protective interventions while minimizing systemic confounding factors inherent to *in vivo* models.

Effects of the compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6 on isolated rat brain synaptosomes

On isolated rat-brain synaptosomes, administered alone at a concentration of 100 μM , the compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6 revealed low statistically significant neurotoxic effects on synaptosomal viability and the level of GSH compared to the control (non-treated synaptosomes). Compound Y1 decreased synaptosomal viability by 35% and the GSH level by 40%; compounds Y2 and Y4 decreased synaptosomal viability by 70% and the GSH level by 35%. Compound Y6 decreased synaptosomal viability by 25% and the GSH level by 35% compared to the control (Fig. 2).

Effects of the compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6 on isolated rat brain mitochondria

On isolated rat-brain mitochondria, administered alone at a concentration of 100 μM , the compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6 again revealed low statistically significant neurotoxic effects on MDA production and the level of GSH compared to the control (non-treated mitochondria). Compounds Y1 and Y4 decreased the GSH level by 30% and increased MDA production by 35%, while compounds Y2 and Y6 decreased the GSH level by 20% and increased MDA production by 40% compared to the control (Fig. 3).

Effects of the compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6 on isolated rat brain microsomes

On isolated rat-brain microsomes, administered alone at a concentration of 100 μM , the compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and

Figure 2. Effects of the compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6, administered alone at a concentration of 100 μM , on synaptosomal viability and the GSH level.

Figure 3. Effects of the compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6, administered alone at a concentration of 100 μM , on MDA production and the GSH level in isolated rat-brain mitochondria.

Y6 revealed low statistically significant pro-oxidant effects on levels of MDA compared to the control (non-treated microsomes). Compounds Y1 and Y4 increased MDA production by 50%, and compounds Y2 and Y6 by 40%, compared to the control (non-treated microsomes) (Fig. 4).

The neuroprotective effects of the investigated compounds were evaluated at distinct subcellular levels using three established models of neurotoxicity: the 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA) model to assess protection at the synaptosomal level; the *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (*t*-BuOOH)-induced oxidative stress model to determine protection at the mitochondrial level; and the classical non-enzymatic lipid peroxidation model based on iron/ascorbate-induced peroxidation to evaluate protective effects at the microsomal level.

The first animal model created to resemble Parkinson's disease was the 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA) model,

which is introduced intracerebrally. This model has been used extensively to induce lesions in the nigrostriatal dopaminergic system of rodents. 6-OHDA does not cross the blood-brain barrier effectively, necessitating its direct injection into the substantia nigra pars compacta or striatum over 4–6 weeks. Thus, it can mimic the gradual progression of the neurodegenerative process of Parkinson's disease (PD) in humans. After its injection, 6-OHDA passes into dopaminergic neurons via the dopamine transporter and enters the cytosol, where it undergoes auto-oxidation, leading to the production of ROS and mitochondrial respiratory dysfunction. Because 6-OHDA has a high affinity for the dopamine transporter, it selectively damages dopaminergic neurons by generating ROS. Often, 6-OHDA is administered unilaterally because the lethality of bilateral injection of this compound into the striatum is higher. On the other hand, under the action of MAOB, 6-OHDA is

** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated microsomes).

Figure 4. Effects of the compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6, administered alone at a concentration of 100 μM , on MDA production in isolated rat-brain microsomes.

metabolized to the reactive metabolite *p*-quinone, which also generates an overproduction of ROS and reduces to a significant extent the level of GSH, the main cellular protector (Xue and Bian 2015). Administered alone at a concentration of 150 μM , 6-OHDA revealed a statistically significant neurotoxic effect by decreasing synaptosomal viability and the GSH level by 50% compared to the control (non-treated synaptosomes) (Fig. 5).

In this model of neurotoxicity, compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6 at a concentration of 50 μM revealed good statistically significant neuroprotective effects. Compounds Y1 and Y2 preserved synaptosomal viability by 40% and the GSH level by 30% compared to the control (toxic 6-OHDA). Compound Y4 preserved synaptosomal via-

bility by 60% and the GSH level by 30%. Compound Y6 preserved synaptosomal viability by 60% and the GSH level by 40% compared to the toxic agent (Fig. 5).

Another suitable model of oxidative stress is the use of *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (*t*-BuOOH), which has mitochondrial and microsomal metabolism. Its metabolism to free radical formation proceeds through several steps. In microsomal suspension, in the absence of NADPH, it undergoes a one-electron oxidation to a peroxy radical (reaction 1), whereas in the presence of NADPH, it undergoes a one-electron reduction to an alkoxy radical (reaction 2). In isolated mitochondria and intact cells, *t*-BuOOH undergoes β -cleavage to a methyl radical (reaction 3).

All these radicals trigger a process of lipid peroxidation and reduce the level of GSH (O'Donnell and Burkitt 1994).

Administered alone, *t*-BuOOH at a concentration of 75 μM revealed a statistically significant neurotoxic effect by decreasing the GSH level by 50% and increasing MDA production by 150% compared to the control (non-treated mitochondria) (Fig. 6).

In this model of neurotoxicity, compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6 at a concentration of 50 μM revealed good statistically significant neuroprotective and antioxidant effects. Compounds Y1 and Y2 preserved the GSH level by 60% and decreased MDA production by 60% compared to *t*-BuOOH, while compounds Y4 and Y6 preserved the GSH level by 50% and decreased MDA production by 40% compared to the toxic agent (Fig. 6).

*** $P < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated synaptosomes).

+ $P < 0.05$; ++ $P < 0.01$; +++ $P < 0.001$ vs. control (6-OHDA).

Figure 5. Effects of the compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6, in combination at a concentration of 50 μM with 6-OHDA (150 μM), on synaptosomal viability and the GSH level.

*** $P < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated mitochondria).

** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$ vs. control (t-BuOOH).

Figure 6. Effects of the compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6, in combination at a concentration of 50 μM with *t*-BuOOH (75 μM), on MDA production and the GSH level in isolated rat-brain mitochondria.

A classic model of lipid peroxidation (non-enzymatic) is iron/ascorbate-induced peroxidation. Administered alone, the combination of iron with ascorbic acid increased MDA production by 250% compared to the control. In this combination, a Fenton reaction occurs, which leads to increased production of $\text{OH}\cdot$ radicals (Fig. 7).

In this model on rat-brain microsomes, compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6 revealed good statistically significant antioxidant effects. Compounds Y1, Y2, and Y4 decreased MDA production by 66%, while compound Y6 decreased it by 63%, compared to the toxic agent (Fig. 7).

*** $P < 0.001$ vs. control (Fe/AA).

Figure 7. Effects of the compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6 at a concentration of 50 μM in combination with Fe/AA on MDA production in isolated rat-brain microsomes.

Conclusion

Azomethine compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6 were successfully synthesized via a classical condensation reaction between the corresponding hydrazide and aldehydes in the presence of glacial acetic acid as a catalyst. The reactions proceeded smoothly and afforded pure solid products, confirming the efficiency and applicability of the employed synthetic approach.

Administered alone at a concentration of 100 μM , compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6 revealed low statistically significant neurotoxic effects on isolated rat-brain subcellular fractions (synaptosomes, mitochondria, and microsomes).

On different models of neurotoxicity (6-hydroxydopamine—in synaptosomes, *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide—in mitochondria, and iron/ascorbate—in microsomes), compounds Y1, Y2, Y4, and Y6 at a concentration of 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ revealed good neuroprotective and antioxidant effects compared to the neurotoxic agents.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: Permit from the BFSA No. 347 valid until 27.03.2028.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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